

Pest Control and Management

WEEDS

Ludwigia species — most prevalent broad-leaved weeds in wet zone ricefields of Sri Lanka

J. P. N. R. Chandrasena, Botany Department, University of Colombo, P.O. Box 1490, Colombo 3, Sri Lanka

We surveyed ricefield weeds in four major rice-growing districts in the wet zone (western and southern provinces) of Sri Lanka 1984-85. Villages were sampled according to a probability proportionate to the area under cultivation in each district, based on Department of Census and Statistics data. Two ricefields per village, 1 km apart, were taken randomly. The ricefields surveyed were regarded as reasonably representative of rice-growing conditions in each district.

Both narrow-leaved and broad-leaved species were counted in each field and frequency of occurrence determined for all major weed species. Level of infestation of each major weed was assessed on the basis of visual estimation of weed cover.

Isachne globosa (Thunb.) Kuntze, *Fimbristylis miliacea* (L.) Vahl, *Cyperus iria* L., *Ischaemum rugosum* Salisb., *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) Beauv., and *Echinochloa colona* (L.) Link were the dominant narrow-leaved weeds at all four sites (see table).

Two species of *Ludwigia* appeared to be the most prevalent broad-leaved weeds. *Ludwigia hyssopifolia* (G. Don) Exell was the most frequent broad-leaved species, with moderate to heavy infestations in most fields surveyed. In addition to being found within the field or on bunds, the species also grew luxuriantly along the numerous minor waterways, streams, and irrigation canals.

Ludwigia decurrens Walt. was recorded for the first time in Sri Lanka. A relatively recent introduction to the island, it is spreading rapidly in the wet zone. It was well-established in Kalutara

Occurrence and levels^a of infestation of *Ludwigia hyssopifolia* and *L. decurrens* in 4 ricegrowing districts in the wet zone of Sri Lanka, 1984-85.

District	Fields (no.) sampled	Fields (no.) with given level of infestations ^b					Frequency of occurrence (%)
		0	1	2	3	4	
<i>L. hyssopifolia</i>							
Gampaha	176	9	14	93	57	3	94.8
Colombo	80	4	21	26	20	9	95.0
Kalutara	168	4	48	77	36	3	97.6
Galle	234	14	63	121	32	4	94.0
<i>L. decurrens</i>							
Gampaha	176	158	10	8	—	—	11.4
Colombo	80	14	4	31	22	9	82.5
Kalutara	168	18	40	61	47	2	89.3
Galle	234	226	—	4	2	2	3.5

^a 0 = weed species not observed, 1 = a few plants, 2 = occasional patches (weed cover 10-25% of area assessed), 3 = weed widespread throughout field (weed cover 26-50% of area assessed), 4 = dense and severe infestation (weed cover 51-75% of area assessed), and 5 = weed dominant, masking crop (weed cover 76-100%). ^b Neither weed attained 76-100% coverage.

and Colombo districts, with moderate to heavy infestations in most fields surveyed. In 1985, it occurred in only 10% of the fields surveyed in Gampaha district and 3.5% of those in Galle district.

Farmer interviews revealed that both

species are troublesome. Their extensive root system and rapid growth rate may lead to the removal of large amounts of nutrients added to rice. Currently, control is by hand-pulling, particularly of larger plants. □

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OTHER PESTS

Striga densiflora Benth., an angiospermic root parasite of rice in Bangladesh

M.I. Zuberi, A. Ahmad, M.A.R. Biswas, G. P. Ghosh, A. N. M.A. Choudhury, and P. C. Roy, Botany Department, University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Striga densiflora Benth., a member of the Scrophulariaceae, has been reported as a noxious root parasite causing extensive damage to sugarcane crops in northern Bangladesh. In the 1986 dry season, we observed *Striga* parasitizing rice plants from Harian (Rajshahi) and from Rajbari. In 1987, in adjacent regions of Ishurdi, we found a number

Table 1. Damage caused by *Striga* in sugarcane and ricefields of Ishurdi, Bangladesh, 1987.

	Sugarcane	Rice
Fields surveyed (no.)	38	24
Fields infested (no.)	33	18
Fields totally damaged (no.)	10	4
<i>Striga</i> parasite (no./m ²)	84	37
Host plants (no./m ²)	5	221

of ricefields heavily infested with this angiospermic root parasite, with extensive damage to the premonsoon broadcast (Aus) rice crop (Table 1).

Infested plants were severely stunted with smaller leaves (Table 2). They failed to produce flag leaves; heavy infestations killed the rice plants. In